

SOURCES OF STUDENTS' PERCEIVED AFFECTIVE FILTERS IN AN ESL CLASSROOM

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ABSTRACT

In order to ascertain the sources of students' perceived affective filters in an ESL classroom, the study grouped senior high school students in one of the public schools in the northern Philippines according to the program they were enrolled in and their self-perceived English-speaking performance level during the 2023–2024 academic year. The triangulation method, which includes questionnaires, interviews, and observation, was employed by the researchers to gather data. The majority of students in all strands believe they speak English at an intermediate level, according to the study's findings. Eight criteria on the psychological barriers that can impede language learning, known as the affective filter's sources were found: (a) naturally silent and shy, (b) fear to commit error, (c) lack of skills to speak English, (d) difficulty of the task, (e) intimidation from classmates, (f) fear to be laughed at, (g) intimidation from teachers and (h) bad experience in speaking.

Keywords: Affective Filter, Expressions, ESL Classroom

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INTRODUCTION

In language learning, emotion and cognition are identified as factors that need to be considered. Many times, teachers have observed scenarios in which students struggle to share ideas in class, not because of a lack of knowledge, but because of a level of shyness that inhibits them from performing better in their English classes. Gender equality is seen both as a human rights issue and as a precondition for, and indicator of, sustainable people-centered development (Haack, K., 2014).

In the context of ESL teaching and learning, students' communication readiness is affected by motivation. He (2016) states that motivation is an inner power that allows learners to love speaking English, and regardless of motivation, a strong desire to succeed and excel in oral communication will increase study interest.

In the study conducted by Stark (2019), students with a strong desire to succeed are more likely to keep learning and get better grades than those with a weaker desire. This shows that building motivation to learn is important for every teacher to help them improve students' oral English proficiency, which affects their academic performance. On the other hand, Juhana (2012) opines that arguably the failure of teachers to urge learners to use English in class is the primary cause of the learners' unwillingness to speak the language themselves.

According to Banjong (2015), a lack of fluency in spoken English has a negative impact on students' self-esteem. This is due to the fact that many students struggle to deal with the peculiarities of the target language that they are learning. Low self-esteem has repercussions not only in the daily life of the learners but also, potentially, in their academic accomplishments. This goes to show that students who struggle with their confidence tend to be reserved, unwilling to speak out in class, and unable to formulate logical statements while they are there. Furthermore, according to Juhana (2012), some of the factors that contribute to a lack of self-confidence are the fear of making errors, the fear of being laughed at, and the fear of receiving poor marks. Learners who struggle with low levels of self-confidence in the speaking classroom will consequently have less opportunity to practice, resulting in difficulty expressing themselves in English (Gabejan, 2021).

Researchers in the field of language learning, such as Alrabai (2014) and Wu (2010), found that anxiety is one of the biggest problems that EFL learners face when trying to learn a language. This denotes that language anxiety is a sort of situational anxiety that stems from the novel circumstances of formal language study, and more specifically from a person's negative perception of their own communicative ability in the target language (Djafri & Wimbari, 2018).

In one of the public senior high schools in northern Philippines, teachers observed in their English classes in all strands and tracks that students' negative emotions such as a lack of motivation, self-confidence, and learning anxiety act as filters that impede and obstruct language learning. Krashen's (1982) view that a number of 'affective variables' play a facilitative, but non-causal, role in second language acquisition is embodied in the Affective Filter hypothesis. Motivation, self-confidence, anxiety, and personality traits are examples of these variables. Krashen (1982) contends that learners with high motivation, self-confidence, a positive self-image, a low level of anxiety, and extroversion are better prepared for second language acquisition success. Low motivation, low self-esteem, anxiety, introversion, and inhibition can all raise the affective filter and create a 'mental block,' preventing comprehensible input from being used for acquisition. In other words, when the filter is turned on, language acquisition is hampered. Positive affect, on the other hand, is required but not sufficient for acquisition to occur.

In this study, the researchers identified the affective filters in senior high school English teaching. The results of the study were used as a basis for the researchers to improve the teaching of the second language. Moreover, the results were used to come up with an intervention to help English teachers in their L2 instruction to adhere to the recommendation of the regional office to develop new contextualized learning resources focusing on the learning areas with low MPS. Thus, this study was conceived.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This research endeavored to determine the sources and expressions of students' perceived affective filters in an ESL classroom.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the student- respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 strand/ program enrolled in
 - 1.2 self- perceived English-speaking performance level

METHODOLOGY AND TOOLS

The study made use of the Mixed Method Design, specifically the sequential-explanatory design. The participants were the senior high school students in one of the public senior high schools in northern Philippines.

The classes observed were chosen using availability sampling. Cochran's formula was used to identify student samples. The data on the school's population was obtained from the registrar. For stratified sampling, the total size of each track/specialization was determined. Because the learners are heterogeneously mixed, stratified sampling was used to determine the respondents. To obtain the samples, the percentage of respondents per track/strand was computed from the population of each grade level.

Permission from the school principal was sought prior to the study's conduct. A request letter was sent for the administration of questionnaires, interviews, and observations. The observation was scheduled after the questionnaires had been distributed. Teachers were given a schedule of when they were observed for research purposes. Following the analysis of the questionnaires, students were interviewed. Those who are identified during the observation were subjected to the interview. A random interview with respondents was also conducted solely to validate the questionnaire results. After compiling the observed manifestations of affective filters and the responses of the students in the series of interviews, the interview for teachers was administered. Interview permission was sought as a courtesy, and the interview took place during the teachers' free time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile Of Student- Respondents

Table 1: Profile of Respondents based on Strands

STRAND	N	%
ABM	109	13.30%
ARTS & DESIGN	37	4.50%
GAS	109	13.30%
HUMMS	197	24.10%
SPORTS	37	4.40%
STEM	196	24.00%
TVL	133	16.30%

The breakdown of students by academic strand is shown in Table 1. Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMMS), with 197 students, comprising 24.10% of the overall student body, was the strand with the largest number of students. Following closely behind, with 196 students, or 24.00% of the total, was Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM). 16.30% of the total, or 133 students, were enrolled in the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) strand. Thirteen percent of the students were enrolled in the General Academic Strand (GAS) and the Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) strand, which each had 109 students. With 37 students apiece, or 4.50% of the total student body, Arts & Design and Sports had the fewest number of students.

Table 2: Self- perceived English-Speaking Performance Level

STRAND	Self- perceived English-Speaking Performance Level							
	<i>Beginning</i>		<i>Intermediate</i>		<i>Advanced</i>		<i>Superior</i>	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
ABM	14	12.8%	72	66.1%	23	21.1%	0	0
ARTS & DESIGN	23	62.2%	14	37.8%	0	0.0%	0	0
GAS	27	24.8%	59	54.1%	23	21.1%	0	0
HUMMS	45	22.8%	120	60.9%	32	16.2%	0	0
SPORTS	23	62.2%	14	37.8%	0	0.0%	0	0
STEM	11	5.6%	143	73.0%	42	21.4%	0	0
TVL	64	48.1%	68	51.1%	1	0.8%	0	0

Table 2 presents the self-perceived English-speaking performance level of students across different strands. The performance levels are categorized as Beginning, Intermediate, Advanced, and Superior. The number and percentage of students in each category are provided for each strand. In the ABM strand, most students (66.1%) perceive themselves as being at the Intermediate level, followed by 21.1% at the Advanced level, and 12.8% at the Beginning level. In the Arts & Design and Sports strands, a majority of students (62.2%) perceive themselves as being at the Beginning level, while 37.8% rate themselves as Intermediate. In the GAS strand, more than half of the students (54.1%) perceive themselves as Intermediate, followed by 24.8% at the Beginning level, and 21.1% at the Advanced level. In the HUMMS strand, a majority of students (60.9%) perceive themselves as Intermediate, followed by 22.8% at the Beginning level, and 16.2% at the Advanced level. In the STEM strand, a large majority of students (73.0%) perceive themselves as Intermediate, followed by 21.4% at the Advanced level, and 5.6% at the Beginning level. In the TVL strand, the students are almost evenly split between the Beginning (48.1%) and Intermediate (51.1%) levels. Only a small fraction (0.8%) perceives themselves as Advanced.

The findings imply that the majority of students in all strands believe they speak English at an intermediate level. No student gave themselves a Superior rating. There are some noticeable distinctions within the strands, though, with a greater percentage of students evaluating themselves at the Beginning level in the Arts & Design and Sports strands than in the other strands. On the other hand, the largest percentage of students who rate themselves as Advanced in the STEM strand.

The results support the claim of Dev and Qiqieh (2016) which explains that to be a language proficient, students should demonstrate not only fluency but accuracy as well, and that can be considered as educational achievement. Non-native English-speaking students consider having English language proficiency as an educational goal, which is the academic achievement. Therefore, they get to feel more confident and more belonging because of their achievement and proficiency, which lead them to be more involved in the society.

In the Philippines, English language teachers were held responsible for the decline of “English standards” (Wilson, 2009). Specifically, Wilson (2009) considered the International English Language Testing System (IELTS) results of the Filipinos who were looking for jobs in other countries for 2008 alarming. It turned out that Malaysians got higher overall mean scores in English than Filipinos who were well-known for their ability in English.

Not just Filipino learners articulated problems regarding English language learning. Even among Korean college students who studied here in the Philippines revealed that they had difficulty both in their English subject and in the actual use of this language while talking to Filipinos (de Guzman, et al., 2006). Similarly, foreign students enrolled in the Universities here in the country expressed that they also experienced apprehension in their English language learning (Lucas, Miraflores & Go, 2011). However, they were able to compensate for this negative feeling by employing a strategy enhancing their vocabulary.

Perceived Sources of Students' Affective Filter

Table 3: Sources of Affective filters

Sources of Affective Filter	Mean Rank	Final Rank
Fear to commit error	3.69	1
Difficulty of the task	3.71	2
Naturally silent and shy	3.83	3
Intimidation from teacher	4.10	4
Intimidation from classmates	4.44	5
Lack of skills to speak in English	4.6	6
Fear to be laughed at	5.19	7
Bad experience in speaking	6.41	8

Table 3 presents an overview of the psychological barriers that can impede language learning, known as the affective filter's sources. Eight criteria were found, and their mean scores were used to rank them. Fear of making mistakes was the component that was placed highest, meaning it had the lowest mean score and was therefore the most significant ($M = 3.69$). This was closely followed by the task's difficulty ($M = 3.71$) and shyness and silence as innate tendencies ($M = 3.83$). Other contributing factors were lack of English speaking ability ($M = 4.6$), intimidation by students ($M = 4.44$), and intimidation from the teacher ($M = 4.10$). The dread of ridicule ($M = 5.19$) and negative speaking experiences ($M = 6.41$, Rank = 8) were ranked.

According to Banjong (2015), a lack of fluency in spoken English has a negative impact on students' self-esteem. This is due to the fact that many students struggle to deal with the peculiarities of the target language that they are learning. Learners who struggle with low levels of self-confidence in the speaking classroom will consequently have less opportunity to practice, resulting in difficulty expressing themselves in English.

Table 4: Sources of Affective filters of Learners grouped by Strand

Sources of Affective Filter	STRAND													
	ABM		ARTS & DESIGN		GAS		HUMMS		SPORTS		STEM		TVL	
	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank
Lack of skills to speak in English	3.01	2	1.54	1	6.2	7	4.15	3	6.81	7	3.64	2	6.94	7
Fear to commit error	6.02	7	4.57	4	5.44	6	2.51	2	1.84	1	2.24	1	4.47	5
Fear to be laughed at	6.15	8	5.27	5	6.83	8	6.46	7	4.35	4	3.79	3	3.47	3
Intimidation from classmate	5.72	6	3.62	3	2.34	1	4.58	4	5.35	5	4.92	5	4.15	4
Intimidation from teacher	4.7	5	5.65	6	2.61	2	4.61	5	4.35	4	4.92	5	2.35	2
Difficulty of the task	3.7	3	2.41	2	3.34	3	5.33	6	3.46	3	3.98	4	1.66	1
Bad experience in speaking	4.32	4	6.3	8	5.16	5	6.51	8	7.43	8	7.16	7	7.61	8
Naturally silent and shy	2.39	1	5.92	7	4.08	4	1.85	1	2.41	2	5.34	6	5.35	6

The study examined the sources of affective filter across different strands of study. Table 4 presents mean scores and ranks for each source were calculated for each strand. In the ABM strand, students who were naturally silent and shy had the lowest mean score ($M = 2.39$), indicating that this was the most significant source of affective filter. However, in the ARTS & DESIGN strand, the lack of skills to speak in English was the most significant source ($M = 1.54$). Interestingly, in the GAS strand, intimidation from classmates was the most significant source ($M = 2.34$), which differs from the other strands. This suggests that the social dynamics in the GAS strand might be different from the others. In the HUMMS strand, students who were naturally silent and shy also had the lowest mean score ($M = 1.85$), similar to the ABM strand. This suggests that personality traits might play a significant role in these strands. In the SPORTS strand, fear to commit error was the most significant source ($M = 1.84$), indicating that the pressure to perform might be high in this strand. In the STEM strand, fear to commit error was also the most significant source ($M = 2.24$), suggesting that the academic demands in this strand might be high. Finally, in the TVL strand, difficulty of the task was the most significant source ($M = 1.66$), indicating that the practical nature of the tasks in this strand might pose a challenge to the students.

Low self-esteem has repercussions not only in the daily life of the learners but also, potentially, in their academic accomplishments. This goes to show that students who struggle with their confidence tend to be reserved, unwilling to speak out in class, and unable to formulate logical statements while they are there. Furthermore, according to Juhana (2012), some of the factors that contribute to a lack of self-confidence are the fear of making errors, the fear of being laughed at, and the fear of receiving poor marks.

Table 5: Sources of Affective filters of Learners grouped by English-Speaking Skill Proficiency Level

Sources of Affective Filter	English-Speaking Skill Proficiency Level					
	Beginning		Intermediate		Advanced	
	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank
Naturally silent and shy	4.72	5	3.70	2	2.83	1
Fear to commit error	4.00	4	3.58	1	3.57	2
Lack of skills to speak in English	5.33	7	4.41	5	4.13	3
Difficulty of the task	2.89	1	3.89	3	4.38	4
Intimidation from classmates	3.94	3	4.62	6	4.55	5
Fear to be laughed at	4.86	6	5.39	7	4.98	6
Intimidation from teacher	3.71	2	3.99	4	5.21	7
Bad experience in speaking	6.47	8	6.39	8	6.35	8

The study examined the sources of affective filter across different levels of English-speaking skill proficiency: beginning, intermediate, and advanced. Table 5 shows that the mean scores and ranks for each source were calculated for each proficiency level.

For the beginning level, the difficulty of the task was the most significant source of affective filter ($M = 2.89$), followed by intimidation from the teacher ($M = 3.71$), and intimidation from classmates ($M = 3.94$). However, lack of skills to speak in English, which is often considered a major barrier, was ranked 7th ($M = 5.33$). At the intermediate level, fear to commit error was the most significant source ($M = 3.58$), followed by naturally silent and shy ($M = 3.70$), and difficulty of the task ($M = 3.89$). Interestingly, fear to be laughed at was ranked as the least significant source ($M = 5.39$). For the advanced level, naturally silent and shy was the most significant source ($M = 2.83$), followed by fear to commit error ($M = 3.57$), and lack of skills to speak in English ($M = 4.13$). Intimidation from the teacher was ranked as the least significant source ($M = 5.21$).

This emphasizes how crucial it is to provide an emotionally safe learning environment since it is necessary for students to feel motivated and challenged to learn (Turner & Meyer, 2004). Students feel at ease and happy in emotionally supportive learning situations (Patrick, Turner, Meyer, & Midgley, 2003).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In the light of the finding, these suggest that as English-speaking proficiency improves, the sources of affective filter change. For example, while lack of skills to speak in English is a significant source at the beginning level, it becomes less significant as proficiency improves. On the other hand, being naturally silent and shy becomes more significant at the advanced level. This indicates that interventions to reduce the affective filter should be tailored to the specific needs of learners at different proficiency levels.

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